

THE ROLE OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE STUDENTS

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Annotation: Consider the organization of independent work of students in the context of the competence-based approach. It was revealed that realized in practice, federal state educational standards of vocational education of the third-generation professional programs, qualifying characteristics IT specialists show a significant share of the allocation of time for self-study students.

Key words: competence, independent work of students, imagination, efficiency, quality.

Independent work as an integral part of the pedagogical process multifunctional. Participation in it develops the personality, shapes its cognitive interests and cognitive needs, contributes to the formation of interest in the profession and professional aspirations. The personal significance of students' independent work is manifested primarily in the fact that the knowledge, abilities, skills acquired during it affect the entire cognitive sphere: thinking, memory, imagination, feelings, will. Student independent work (SWS) contributes to the development of students' competence: the ability to organize their own activities, choose standard methods and ways of performing professional tasks, evaluate them efficiency and quality, make decisions and be responsible for decisions made. That is, independent work is a significant factor contributing to the development professional competencies of future technicians operating multi-channel telecommunication systems. As can be seen from the above definitions and interpretations, this type of educational activity is considered, on the one hand, as a type of activity that stimulates activity, independence, cognitive interest, and as the basis for self-education, an impetus for further professional development, and on the other hand, as a system of activities or pedagogical conditions that provide guidance for students' independent activities.

A student's independent work can be either in-class work, that is, performed during scheduled classes, or extra-curricular and includes:

- performing independent tasks in laboratory and theoretical workshops, seminars and practical classes;
- work on individual topics of academic disciplines;
- performing tests and coursework;
- undergoing internships and performing the tasks provided for by them;
- preparation for all types of control tests;
- preparation for final certification and completion of qualifying final work;
- participation in scientific and scientific-methodological work, in scientific and scientific-practical conferences and seminars.

Designing modern educational programs require the specification of new methods, forms and technologies of training aimed at developing professional competence. In

particular, the competency-based approach makes its own demands on the organization of students' independent work.

Requirements for training an independent, active, competent specialist, in accordance with the modern needs of a unified information society are set out in state educational standards. Modernization of modern vocational education involves increasing the independence of students in order to develop in them the necessary skills to master new information in the field of professional activity and effectively adapt to new working conditions. In the process of training competitive mid-level specialists, it is necessary to pay special attention to the formation of professional and personal qualities. The federal state educational standards for secondary vocational education of the third generation, professional programs, and qualification characteristics of specialists in the communications industry, implemented in practice, show a significant share of the distribution of time for independent work of students.

One of the important tasks of the higher education system is to develop the creative abilities of students, strengthen their need for knowledge, and prepare potential professionals who are able to solve problems through the development of independent thinking skills. In particular, the rapid modernization and technological equipping of important sectors of our economy is considered a priority of our society, which requires serious attention. Personnel trained according to general qualification requirements for obtaining a bachelor's degree in state educational standards have the ability to make independent decisions in their field, have competitive professional training, and organize their work on a scientific basis and independently. improve your knowledge and skills. In the higher education system, independent education plays a special role in training personnel with these characteristics. It is known that one of the important factors in training qualified personnel is to improve the quality and efficiency of training. Modern methods, forms and means of teaching, gaming technologies, problem-based learning and independent learning play an important role in improving the quality and effectiveness of learning. This requires in-depth scientific and pedagogical research to develop the content of independent learning for students in higher educational institutions (HEIs) and improve the methods of its organization and implementation.

Of course, in many universities there are great opportunities for students to study independently theoretically and practically. However, in many cases, the formation of skills and abilities of independent learning in the educational process is not considered an urgent pedagogical problem, the analysis and development of the content of independent learning is not suitable from a modern point of view, insufficient attention is paid to its study. effective methods, forms and tools. These and other similar questions show that there are a number of pedagogical problems in the organization, implementation, and control of independent learning of students in the preparation of bachelors in higher educational institutions. The need to study these issues from a scientific and pedagogical point of view, taking into account the needs of students for independent learning and creating adequate conditions for independent learning, the professionalism of teachers of higher educational institutions in the organization, implementation and control of independent learning, as a result of insufficient pedagogical training, insufficient knowledge, skills and abilities of students in independent learning, lack of educational and methodological literature, recommendations, developments, guidelines, instructions for organizing, implementing and monitoring students' independent

learning. Some bachelors who have received higher education do not fully develop the skills of independent decision-making, and the ability to defend their views indicates the relevance of the problem.

Independent work of students plays a key role in the formation of competence. After all, a future specialist is required not only to have knowledge and skills, but also to be able to apply them in practice. This can be achieved by teaching students to independently solve problems in the educational process [6]. Based on this general goal, independent education accustoms future specialists to the full use of their intellectual potential in any situation and context, to search for the necessary knowledge, and to apply it in practice. In short, it prepares you to function as a productive, competitive professional in public life and the workplace. During the student period, skills and abilities of independent learning are formed in collaboration with the teacher based on his advice. The curriculum, syllabus and textbooks have been mastered. They are taught to apply in practice to achieve guaranteed results. In this process, it is useful to focus as much as possible on the student's independent activities. One of the benefits of self-directed learning in higher education is that a student can seek out and enrich knowledge related to their profession and specialization in addition to the curriculum and textbooks. This, in turn, will lead to the formation of proactive, creative and imaginative personnel. Self-directed learning creates positive competition among students. By learning from each other, they channel their minds, energy and time into useful pursuits. When preparing for various competitions, participating in scientific Olympiads and striving for victory, participating in scientific and creative exhibitions, unknown aspects of student talent are revealed. The student's self-confidence, intelligence and abilities increase. Self-directed education also has a positive impact on the development of young people as individuals. It involves stabilization of character traits, especially strengthening of strong-willed qualities, improvement of qualities such as self-control. They are accustomed to being indifferent to things and events in the environment, being able to correctly evaluate them, expressing and proving their independent opinion.

Also, students should receive from the teacher a clear goal for independent work with terminology in the specialty, detailed instructions on its content, techniques and methods of implementation. It is very important to reorient students from reproductive methods of work to creative activities.

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